

Impact Factor: 5.479

ISSN 2181-9505

Doi Journal 10.26739/2181-9505

Philosophy and Life

FALSAFA VA HAYOT • ФИЛОСОФИЯ И ЖИЗНЬ

Special
Issue 1

2022

O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI VAZIRLAR MAHKAMASI
HUZURIDAGI IMOM BUXORIY XALQARO
ILMIY-TADQIQOT MARKAZI
O'ZBEKISTON FALSAFA JAMIYATI

Международный научно-
исследовательский центр
Имам Бухари при Кабинете
Министров Республики Узбекистан
Философское общество Узбекистана

Imam Bukhari International
Research Center under the
Cabinet of Ministers of the
Republic of Uzbekistan
Philosophical Society of Uzbekistan

FALSAFA VA HAYOT XALQARO JURNAL

1 MAHCYCS CON

ФИЛОСОФИЯ И ЖИЗНЬ МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ
СПЕЦИАЛЬНЫЙ НОМЕР 1

PHILOSOPHY AND LIFE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL
SPECIAL ISSUE 1

Jurnal bir yilda 4
marta nashr qilinadi.

Журнал выходит
4 раза в год.

The journal is published
4 times in a year.

ISSN: 2181-9505
DOI: 10.26739/2181-9505

2022

FALSAFA VA HAYOT XALQARO JURNAL

№SI-1 (2022) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-9505-2022-SI-1>

Tahrir kengashi:

Abdildina, R.J. — Qozog'iston FA akademigi, f.f.d., professor

Askarov, T.A. — Qirg'iziston FA akademigi, f.f.d., professor

Bazarbayev, J. — O'zbekiston FA akademigi, f.f.d., professor

Bashimov, V.V. — Turkmaniston milliy ta'lim instituti direktori

Werner Bush — dunyo professorlari uyushmasi exs prezidenti DSc, professor (Germaniya)

Mamedzade, I.R. — Azarbayjon FA Falsafa va sotsiologiya instituti direktori, f.f.d., professor

Morevedge, P. — AQSH dunyo olimlari departamenti raisi, DSc, professor

Nisanbayev, A.N. — Qozog'iston FA akademigi, f.f.d., professor

Skarantino, L.M. — Jahon falsafa jamiyatlari federatsiyasi prezidenti, DSc, professor, (Italiya)

Smirnov, A.V. — Rossiya FA akademigi, Rossiya FA "Falsafa" instituti direktori, Rossiya Falsafa Jamiyati prezidenti, f.f.d., professor (Rossiya)

Tursunov, A. — Tojikiston FA akademigi, f.f.d., professor (Tojikiston)

Tsuy Veyxan — Xitoy ijtimoiy fanlar Akademiyasi vitse-prezidenti, DSc, professor, (Xitoy)

Chumakov, A.N. — Rossiya FA Falsafa instituti professori, f.f.d., (Rossiya)

Muassislar:

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasi huzuridagi Imom al Buxoriy xalqaro ilmiy - tadqiqot markazi

O'zbekiston falsafa jamiyati
OOO tadqiqot.uz

Vazirlar Mahkamasi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiyasi komissiyasi rayosatining qarori bilan maxsus jurnallar ro'yxatiga kiritildi. 2018-yil 29-dekabrda 260/7 sonli bayonnoma

Ro'yxatga olinganligi haqidagi 1175 sonli guvohnoma O'zbekiston matbuot va axborot agentligi tomonidan 20.02.2018 yilda berilgan.

Bosh muharrir:

Shermuhamedova, N.A., — f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Muhamedova, Z.M., — f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)

Mas'ul muharrir:

Safayeva, S.X., — f.f.n., dotsent (O'zbekiston)

Tahrir hay'ati:

Allahyarova, T. — f.f.d., professor (Azarbayjon)

Andirjanova, G.A., — s.f.d., professor (Qozog'iston)

Abasov, A. S. — f.f.d., professor (Azarbayjon)

Ahamer, G. — PhD, professor (Avstriya)

B.K. Santosh Kukreja, — DSc, professor (Hindiston)

Bodio Todeush, — s.f.d., professor (Polsha)

Bilalov, M. I., — f.f.d., professor (Rossiya)

Berna, A., — PhD, professor (Turkiya)

Vefa Tashdelen, — f.f.d., professor (Turkiya)

Gabitov, T. X. — f.f.d., professor (Qozog'iston)

Guseynov, S. — f.f.d., professor (Azarbayjon)

Gezalov, A.A., — f.f.n., professor (Rossiya)

Ivatova, L.M., — s.f.d., professor (Qozog'iston)

Kurmangaliyeva, G.K., — f.f.d., professor (Qozog'iston)

Lazarevich, A.A., — f.f.n., professor (Belorussiya)

Muzaffarov, M. — f.f.d., professor (Tojikiston)

Morevedge, R. — DSc, professor (AQSH)

Naushanbayeva, A., Hakimogli, — PhD filol., professor (Turkiya)

Olatunji Felix. O. — DSc., professor (Nigeriya)

Paxruddinov, Sh. I., — s.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)

Sadikova, N.N., — f.f.d., professor (Tojikiston)

Saifnazarov, I.S., — f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)

Sergeyev, M.Y., — PhD, professor (AQSH)

Telebayev, G.T., — f.f.d. professor (Qozog'iston)

To'rayev, B. O., — f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)

Urmanbetova, J.K., — f.f.d., professor (Qirg'iziston)

Chjan Baychun, — f.f.d., professor (Xitoy)

Shadmonov, Q.B., — f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)

Fishier, A. — f.f.d., professor (Fransiya)

Yaxshilikov, J. — f.f.d., professor (O'zbekiston)

Yaskevich, Y.S., — f.f.d., professor (Belorusiya)

Ilmiy kotib:

Mahkamov, U. (O'zbekiston)

Musahhihlar:

Xidirov, M.T., (O'zbekiston)

Hamdamova, S. (O'zbekiston)

Madiyorova, V. (O'zbekiston)

Saurov, R.R., (O'zbekiston)

ФИЛОСОФИЯ И ЖИЗНЬ МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ

№SI-1 (2022) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-9505-2022-SI-1>

Редакционный совет:

Абдильдина, Р. Ж. - академик НАН Казахстана, д.ф.н., профессор

Аскарров, Т. А. - академик АН Киргизистана, д.ф.н., профессор

Базарбаев, Ж. - академик АН Узбекистана, д.ф.н., профессор

Башимов, В. В. - директор национального института образования Туркменистана

Вернер Буш. - экс президент всемирной ассоциации профессоров, доктор философских наук, профессор, (Германия)

Мамедзаде, И. Р. - д.ф.н., профессор, директор института “Философии и социологии” АН Азербайджана

Мореведж, П. - DSc. профессор, руководитель GSP США

Нысанбаев, А.Н. - академик АН Казахстана, д.ф.н., профессор

Скарантино, Л. М. - президент всемирной федерации философских обществ д.ф.н., профессор (Италия)

Смирнов, А. В. - академик АН России, директор института Философии АН России, президент РФО, д.ф.н., профессор (Россия)

Турсунов, А. - академик АН Таджикистана, д.ф.н., профессор

Цуй Вэйхан - Вице-президент Института философии КАОН, д.ф.н., профессор (Китай)

Чумаков, А. Н. - проф. РАН, д.ф.н., (Россия)

Учредители:

Международный научно-исследовательский Центр Имама аль Бухари при Кабинете Министров Республики Узбекистан
Философское общество Узбекистана,
ООО tadqiqot.uz

Решением Высшей аттестационной комиссии при Кабинете Министров Республики Узбекистан введен в список специальных журналов. 2018 год 29 декабрь протокол №260/7

Регистрационное свидетельство №1175 выдано 27.02.2018 агенством по печати и информации Узбекистана

Главный редактор:

Шермухамедова, Н. А. - д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Заместитель редактора:

Мухамедова, З. М. - д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Ответственный редактор:

Сафаева, С. Х. - к.ф.н., доцент (Узбекистан)

Редакционная коллегия:

Аллахярова, Т. - д.ф.н., профессор (Азербайджан)

Андиржанова, Г. А. - д.п.н., профессор (Казахстан)

Абасов, А. - д.ф.н., профессор (Азербайджан)

Ахамер, Г. - PhD, профессор (Австрия)

В.К.Сантош Кукреджа. - PhD, профессор (Индия)

Бодио Тодеуш. - д.п.н., профессор (Польша)

Билалов, М. И. - д.ф.н., профессор (Россия)

Берна, А. - PhD.- профессор (Турция)

Вефа Ташделен - д.ф.н., профессор (Турция)

Габитов, Т. Х. - д.ф.н., профессор (Казахстан)

Гусейнов, С. -д.ф.н., профессор (Азербайджан)

Гезалов, А.А. - к.ф.н., профессор (Россия)

Иватова, Л. М. - д.п.н., профессор, (Казахстан)

Курмангалиева, Г. К. - д.ф.н., профессор (Казахстан)

Лазаревич, А А - к.ф.н., профессор (Беларусия)

Музаффаров, М. - д.ф.н., профессор (Таджикистан)

Мореведж, Р. — DSc, профессор (США)

Наушабаева, А., Хекимоглы - PhD, профессор (Туркия)

Олатунжи Феликс О. — DSc, профессор (Нигерия)

Пахруддинов, Ш.И. - д.п.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Садикова, Н. Н. - д.ф.н., профессор (Таджикистан)

Саифназаров, И.С. - д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Сергеев, М. Ю. - PhD, профессор (США)

Телебаев, Г.Т. - д.ф.н., профессор (Казахстан)

Тураев, Б.О. - д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Урманбетова, Ж. К. - д.ф.н., профессор (Киргизистан)

Чжан Байчун - д.ф.н., профессор (Китай)

Шадманов, К.Б. - д.ф.н. профессор (Узбекистан)

Фишлер, А. - д.ф.н., профессор (Франция)

Яхшиликов, Ж. - д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Яскевич, Я.С. - д.ф.н., профессор (Беларуссия)

Ученый секретарь:

Махкамов, У. (Узбекистан)

Корректоры:

Хидиров, М.Т. (Узбекистан)

Хамдамова, С. (Узбекистан)

Мадиярова, В. (Узбекистан)

Сауров, Р.Р. (Узбекистан)

PHILOSOPHY AND LIFE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL

№SI-1 (2022) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-9505-2022-SI-1>

Editorial Council:

Abdildina, R.J. - academician AS of Kazakhstan, doctor of philos. sciences, professor
Askarov, T.A. - academician AS of Kyrgyzstan, doctor of philos. sciences, professor;

Bazarbaev, J. - academician AS of Uzbekistan, doctor of philos. sciences, professor

Bashimov B.B. - director of national Institute of education of Turkmenistan

Werner Bush - President of the World Association of Professors, DSc, professor (Germany)

Mamedzade, I.R. - director of Institute “Philosophy and sociology” AS of Azerbaijan doctor of philosophical sciences, professor

Morewedge, P. - Editor-in-Chief; IGDE, DSc, professor USA

Nysanbaev, A.N. - academician AS of Kazakhstan, doctor of philos. sciences, professor

Scarantino, L.M. - President of International Federation of Philosophical societies, professor of philosophy and politics of culture, (Italy)

Smirnov, A.V. - Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Russia, Director of the Institute of Philosophy of the Academy of Sciences of Russia, President RFS, doctor of philos. sciences, professor (Russia)

Tursunov, A. - academician of the ASc of Tajikistan, doctor of philos. sciences, professor

Tsui Weihan - vice-President of the Institute of Philosophy CAAS, doctor of philos. sciences, professor (China)

Chumakov, A.N. - professor RAN doctor of philos. sciences (Russia)

Founders:

Imam al Bukhari International Research Center under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan Philosophical Society of Uzbekistan OOO tadqiqot.uz

By the decision of the Higher Attestation Commission under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan entered into the list of special journals. 2018 December 29 Protocol №260 / 7

The registration certificate № 1175 was issued on February 27, 2018 by the Uzbek Agency for Press and Information

Editor-in-Chief

Shermukhamedova, N.A. - doctor of philos. sciences, professor (Uzbekistan)

Deputy Editor:

Mukhamedova, Z.M. - doctor of philos. sciences, professor (Uzbekistan)

Managing editor:

Safaeva, S.Kh. - Ph.D. philos., (Uzbekistan)

Editorial team:

Allahyarova, T. - doctor of philos. sciences, professor (Azerbaijan)

Andirjanova, G.A. - doctor of political sciences, professor (Kazakhstan)

Abasob, A. S. - doctor of philos. sciences, professor (Azerbaijan)

Ahamer G. - PhD, professor (Austria)

B.K. Santosh Kukredja, - PhD., professor (India)

Bodio Todeus. - doctor of political sciences, professor (Poland)

Bilalov, M.I. - doctor of philos. sciences, professor (Russiya)

Berna, A. - PhD., professor (Turkey)

Vefa Tashdelen. - doctor of philos. sciences, professor (Turkey)

Gabitov, T.H. - doctor of philos. sciences, professor (Kazakhstan)

Guseynov, S. - doctor of philos. sciences, professor (Azerbaijan)

Gezalov, A.A. - PhD. of philos., associate professor (Russia)

Ivatova, L.M. - doctor of political sciences., professor (Kazakhstan)

Kurmangaliyeva, G.K. - doctor of philos., professor (Kazakhstan)

Lazarevich, A. A. - PhD philos., professor (Belarus)

Morewedge, R. - doctor of philology, professor (USA)

Muzaffarov, M. - doctor of philos sciences, professor (Tajikistan)

Naushanbaeva, A., Hakimogli. - PhD. philos., professor (Turkey)

Olatunji, Felix.O. - DSc, professor (Nigeriya)

Pakhrudinov, Sh.I. - doctor of political sciences, professor (Uzbekistan)

Sadikova, N.N. - doctor of philos. sciences, professor (Tajikistan)

Saifnazarov, I.S. - doctor of philos. sciences, professor (Uzbekistan)

Sergeev, M.Yu. — PhD, philos., professor (USA)

Telebaev, G.T. - doctor of philos. sciences, professor (Kazakhstan)

Turaev, B.O. - doctor of philos. sciences, professor (Uzbekistan)

Urmanbetova, J.K. - doctor of philos. sciences, professor (Kyrgyzstan)

Zhang Baichun - doctor of philos. sciences, professor (China)

Shadmanov, Q. - doctor of philos. sciences, professor (Uzbekistan)

Fischler, A. - doctor of philos. sciences, professor (France)

Yaxshllikov, J. - doctor of philos. sciences, professor (Uzbekistan)

Yaskevich, Ya.S. - doctor of philos. sciences, professor (Belarus)

Scientific Secretary:

Mahkhamov, U. (Uzbekistan)

Correctors:

Khidirov, M.T. (Uzbekistan)

Hamdamova, S. (Uzbekistan)

Madiyorova, V. (Uzbekistan)

Saurov, R.R. (Uzbekistan)

1. Абдуллаев Сардор Туйчиевич ГЎЗАЛЛИККА ОИД ФАЛСАФИЙ ҚАРАШЛАРНИНГ ТИЗИМЛИ ТАҲЛИЛИ.....	8
2. Абдумажидова Хамида ВЛИЯНИЕ ИНТЕГРАЦИОННЫХ ПРОЦЕССОВ В ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ НА АКТИВНОСТЬ СОЦИАЛЬНО-ПОЛИТИЧЕСКИХ ОТНОШЕНИЙ.....	18
3. Ашурова Хуршида Сағдуллаевна МАХМУДХЎЖА БЕҲБУДИЙНИНГ МАЪНАВИЙ МЕРОСИ.....	26
4. Ahrorova Madina Rahmatovna O‘ZBEK MUMTOZ SHOIRLARI IJODIDA GENDER TENGLIGI MASALASI.....	33
5. Boltsev Farrukh Farhodovich THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE PHILOSOPHICAL ANALYSIS OF THE INTERACTION OF LANGUAGE, THOUGHT AND CULTURE IN THE CONTEXT OF GLOBALIZATION.....	40
6. Бозоров Мустафо Жабборович “МИГРАЦИЯ” ТУШУНЧАСИНИНГ ФАЛСАФИЙ ТАҲЛИЛИ.....	49
7. Каримов Соҳибназар Каримович РУҲИЙ ПОКЛИК ҲАҚИДАГИ ТАЪЛИМОТ ЁҲУД ТАСАВВУФ ФАЛСАФАСИДА КОМИЛ ИНСОН МАСАЛАСИ.....	57
8. Комилов Рўзи Рабиевич ЎЗБЕК ХАЛҚИ НИКОҲ МАРОСИМЛАРИНИНГ АХЛОҚИЙ ФУНКЦИЯЛАРИ.....	65
9. Мажитов Махмуд Абдимўмин ўғли ИЖТИМОЙ МУҲИТ - ШАҲС ШАКЛЛАНИШИ ЖАРАЁНИ ДЕТЕРМИНАНТИ СИФАТИДА.....	74
10. Махмудова Азиза Нугмановна ФУҚАРОЛИК ЖАМИЯТДА ҲУҚУҚИЙ ТАРБИЯНИНГ ЎРНИ.....	81
11. Меликова Мартаба Нумоновна ФИЛОСОФСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ ДУХОВНОГО НАСЛЕДИЯ АЛИШЕРА НАВОИ.....	88
12. Омонов Баходир Нуриллаевич ЭКОЛОГИК ГЛОБАЛЛАШУВ КОНТЕКСТИДА ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДАГИ ЭКОЛОГИК ВАЗИЯТДАГИ ЎЗГАРИШЛАР.....	95
13. Usmonova Laylo Rahmatullaevna THE EMOTIONAL IMPACT OF ORIENTAL MINIATURES AND ITS ROLE IN THE STUDY OF HUMAN AESTHETIC NEEDS.....	106
14. Фозилова Азиза Иноятиллаевна МИГРАЦИЯ ЖАРАЁНЛАРИНИНГ ЖАҲОН ИЛМ –ФАН ТАРАҚҚИЁТИДАГИ РОЛИ...	114
15. Холиқов Юнус Ортиқович ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА МИЛЛАТЛАРАРО БАҒРИКЕНГЛИК ИНСОНПАРВАРЛИКНИНГ АСОСИЙ ТАМОЙИЛИ СИФАТИДА.....	120

16. Ҳамдамов Ислом Акрамович ИЛМ-ФАН ТАРҚАҚЎИТИДА МИРЗО УЛУҒБЕК ИЛМИЙ МЕРОСИ ВА “ЗИЖИ ЖАДИДИ ГУРАГОНИЙ” АСАРИНИНГ ТУТГАН ЎРНИ.....	128
17. Шерманов Исобек Чилмаматович БИОТЕХНОЛОГИК ЖАРАЁНЛАР ТАРАҚЎИТИДА МОДДИЙ ВА МАЪНАВИЙ ИШЛАБ ЧИҚАРИШ УЙЎУНЛИГИ МАСАЛАЛАРИ.....	135
18. Шеров Мансур Болтаевич ЎЗБЕКИСТОН ҲАРБИЙ ХИЗМАТЧИЛАРИДА КРЕАТИВ ТАФАККУРНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШНИНГ ИЖТИМОИЙ-ФАЛСАФИЙ ЖИҲАТЛАРИ.....	144
19. Makhmudova Aziza Nugmanovna LEGAL-REGULATORY SYSTEM IN CIVIL SOCIETY CONTROL OF THE PROCESS OF LEGAL SOCIALIZATION OF INDIVIDUALS.....	149
20. Гонашвили Александр Сергеевич СОЦИАЛЬНО-ФИЛОСОФСКОЕ ПОНИМАНИЕ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ РУБЕЖА XIX И XX ВЕКОВ: СОЦИАЛЬНО-ИСТОРИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ.....	155
21. Хаджиметов Бехзод Бахадирович ШАРҚ МИНИАТЮРА САНЪАТИДА ПОРТРЕТ ЖАНРИ.....	163
22. Pulatov Jaxongir Nazirovich ЖАМИАТ БАҲАРАР ТАРАҚҚИЙОТИНИ РИВОЛАНТИРИШДА FUQAROLIK ЖАМИАТИ ИНСТИТУТЛАРИНИНГ О’РНИ.....	169
23. Ашуоров Шодмон Шаропович ҒАРБ ФАЙЛАСУФЛАРИНИНГ ИЖТИМОИЙ – ФАЛСАФИЙ ҚАРАШЛАРИДА ЖАМИАТ БАҲАРАРЛИГИ МАСАЛАЛАРИ.....	177
24. Ravshan Mardonov ZAMONAVIY TA’LIM FALSAFASI VA FALSAFIY ANTROPOLOGIYA: TUTASH MUAMMOLAR VA O’ZARO TA’SIR USULLARI.....	184
25. Эргашева Махбуба Хотамбековна ТАЪЛИМДА ИННОВАЦИОН ҒОЯЛАР КИРИБ КЕЛИШИДАГИ ХАОТИК ЖАРАЁНЛАР ҲАМДА ТАЪЛИМ ТИЗИМИДА АТТРАКТОР ОМИЛИ.....	192
26. Эргашева Махбуба Хотамбековна ЗАМОНАВИЙ ТАЪЛИМ СИНЕРГЕТИК ТИЗИМ СИФАТИДА.....	201
27. Саидов Ихтиёр Мизрабович ВАТАНПАРВАРЛИК ТУЙҒУСИНИНГ МАЗМУН-МОҲИЯТИ ВА НАМОЁН БЎЛИШ ШАКЛЛАРИ.....	210
28. Хасанов Миршод Нўмонович ФОРОБИЙНИНГ ФАЛСАФИЙ МЕРОСИНИНГ ТУТГАН ЎРНИ.....	216
29. Elmuradova Surayyo TA’LIM JARAYONINI TASHKIL ETISHNING SHAXSIY EKZISTYENSIAL YONDASHUVINI IJTIMOIY-FALSAFIY Tahlili.....	227
30. Саидова Камола Усканбаевна ЛЮБОВЬ И НЕНАВИСТЬ КАК ДВЕ КРАЙНОСТИ СЕМЕЙНЫХ ОТНОШЕНИЙ.....	232

Makhmudova Aziza Nugmanovna

PhD in Philosophy

Samarkand State Medical Institute, Head of the

Department of Social Sciences and Humanities

e-mail rustamovamaxmudova@bk.ru

LEGAL-REGULATORY SYSTEM IN CIVIL SOCIETY CONTROL OF THE PROCESS OF LEGAL SOCIALIZATION OF INDIVIDUALS

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6589786>

ANNOTATION

The main criterion for achieving the lofty goals set by our country since the first years of independence is to implement the legal framework for achieving these goals through the development of well-thought-out normative documents, the creation of a strong legal system in the country. That is, any state implements its policy by creating a strong legal regulatory system. This article provides a philosophical analysis of the role of social control in the formation of civil society and, most importantly, the role of social control in the legal socialization of the individual. It is no secret that the priority of the reforms is to modernize our legal system following world standards, to make it more humane.

Key words: civil society, individual, public control, legal system, legal system, legal culture, legal practice.

Махмудова Азиза Нугмановна

Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт институти

Ижтимоий ва гуманитар фанлар кафедраси мудири,

фалсафа фанлари доктори (PhD)

rustamovamaxmudova@bk.ru

ФУҚАРОЛИК ЖАМИЯТИДА ҲУҚУҚИЙ-МЕЪЁРИЙ ТИЗИМ ШАХС ҲУҚУҚИЙ ИЖТИМОЙЛАШУВИ ЖАРАЁНИНИ НАЗОРАТИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Мамлакатимиз мустақилликнинг илк йилларидан бошлаб ўз олдида қўйган юксак мақсадларга эришишнинг асосий мезони сифатида ушбу мақсадларга эришишимизнинг ҳуқуқий асосларини, ҳар томонлама чуқур ўйланган норматив ҳужжатларни ишлаб чиқиш, мамлакатда кучли ҳуқуқий меъёрий тизимни яратиш орқали амалга оширишни назарда тутди. Яъни, ҳар қандай давлат ўз сиёсатини кучли ҳуқуқий норматив тизим яратиш орқали амалга оширади. Мазкур мақолада ижтимоий назоратнинг фуқаролик жамиятини шакллантиришдаги аҳамияти ва энг муҳими ижтимоий назоратнинг шахс ҳуқуқий ижтимоийлашувидаги роли масалаларини фалсафий таҳлил қилинган.

Таянч иборалар: фуқаролик жамияти, шахс, жамоатчилик назорати, ҳуқуқ тизими, қонунчилик тизими, ҳуқуқий маданият, ҳуқуқий амалиёт.

INTRODUCTION

Today, humanity is living in the XXI century, a time when human rights are a priority, the process of liberalization in the legal field is accelerating, and man and his life, fundamental rights are recognized as the highest value. The most powerful system for the protection of human dignity is, without a doubt, the legal normative system. Every country today is trying to strengthen the principles of democratization, to develop a strong legal framework for the formation of civil society. "The future and prosperity of our planet depend on how our children develop into human beings ... In this regard, the most important task is to form and educate the minds of people, especially young people, based on enlightenment. We believe that this requires the development of multilateral cooperation in the field of social support of the younger generation, protection of their rights and interests. "

"On Combating Corruption", "On Social Cooperation", "On Public Oversight", "On Measures to Radically Enhance the Role of Civil Society Institutions in the Process of Democratic Renewal of the Country", "On the Concept of Civil Society Development in 2021-2025" We can say that several similar laws are a practical manifestation of the work on the development of civil society in our country, the development of stronger mechanisms for the protection of human rights. After all, the development of any country, the implementation of planned reforms depends in many respects on the high legal culture of its citizens, the level of legal socialization, as well as the legal and regulatory system aimed at protecting human rights.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

So, in this section, we will make a philosophical analysis of what is a legal norm, is the role of the system of legal norms in the legal socialization of the individual, the work being done in our country in this area, and what are the main problems in this area.

"The legal normative system is the internal structure of the law, the internal structure - the structure, which represents the parts of the law and the relationship and proportion between the parts." The legal normative system is a whole system of the interrelated legal system, legislative system, legal culture, and legal practice. There are several interpretations of this concept in scientific research. Russian researcher S.S. Alekseev wondered through which concept it would be possible to fully cover the legal process. Because of the legal system, the system of legal norms means the system of legal norms regulating social relations in society. This is a narrow understanding of the content of this concept and does not fully cover the scope of the concept. It cannot reveal the deep social significance and content of the concept. In a broad sense, the legal system is the legal structure of society, which includes all the phenomena related to law, including legal norms, legal knowledge, legal consciousness, legal culture, legal activity. In the narrow sense, the legal system represents a system of legal norms, a system of norms representing the norms of conduct established by law. In this paragraph, we refer to the legal normative system in the narrow sense, the system of legal norms developed by the state

The legal normative system is a factor that determines the quality and level of control over the process of legal socialization of citizens. It has been carried out in our country in recent years in terms of analyzing the role of the individual in controlling the process of legal socialization.

According to AH Saidov, the development of the legal and regulatory system in our country is based on the following key factors: second, to pursue national interests in building a strong rule of law and a just civil society; third, the correct formation of the balance between personal interests and social interests, the interests of the state; fourth, based on the principles of gradual, membership in the renewal and modernization of the state and society; fifth, based on the principles of openness and transparency, strengthening mechanisms for communication with the people in the discussion and solution of all problems, strengthening cooperation with civil society institutions and international partners in the protection of human rights. "It is obvious that a complex activity has been organized in the development of the legal and regulatory system in our country, with special emphasis on the harmony of universally recognized legal norms and national interests, the joint activities of citizens

and civil society institutions. The goal is to perfect the legal normative system, which serves as a measure of human activity and the legal basis for the development of society.

The legal normative system of legal socialization of the individual in the Republic of Uzbekistan is, first of all, the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The impact of legal socialization of the individual in the process of formation of civil society in Uzbekistan, the issues of regulation of this process by legal normative acts are reflected in our constitution and laws. The second part of the Constitution is entitled "Fundamental rights, freedoms and duties of citizens" and the third part is entitled "Society and the individual", which deals with the process of legal socialization of the individual. In particular, Article 18 of the second part of our Constitution reflects the principle of equality, which has a positive impact on the process of legal socialization in society. Because the belief that citizens, regardless of language, religion, race, gender, or social origin, are equally protected by the state, that they feel an equal and full member of that society, builds a sense of respect for the law and feels protected in that space. . "It is very important in the legal socialization of an individual. After all, legal socialization is, first of all, respect for laws and legal norms. In the formation of civil society and the individual is legal we can also recognize Article 20 of our constitution as an important legal basis and source in socialization. Article 20 of Section 2 of the Constitution stipulates that "citizens must not infringe on the legitimate interests, rights, and freedoms of other persons, the state and society in the exercise of their rights and freedoms." This article reflects the important element of legal socialization of citizens, respect for the law, not to infringe on the rights and freedoms of others in the process of protecting their rights, the timely fulfillment of legal obligations established by the state. It stipulates that each person must respect the rights of other subjects of the legal relationship as a subject of the legal relationship. In addition, the recognition of the rights of citizens to the presumption of personal inviolability and innocence in our constitution is one of the important aspects in the process of legal socialization of the individual. The most important of the external factors influencing a person's legal socialization is that the person feels protected in the society in which he or she lives, untouched by any slander, baseless accusations. This principle is enshrined in Section 2, Article 26 of our Constitution. "Everyone charged with a criminal offense shall be presumed innocent until proved guilty according to the law in a public trial at which he has had all the guarantees necessary for his defense." The accused will be given all the conditions to defend himself in court. " Another important aspect of this article is the right of every citizen to access quality, professional legal protection. This strengthens people's confidence in laws and justice. Along with the basic rights and freedoms of citizens, our Constitution also firmly defines civic duties, which are the second most important aspect of legal socialization. After all, in the legal socialization of a person, it is extremely important that he understands his duties and treats them with respect. In particular, Section 2, Article 48 of the Constitution stipulates that "citizens are obliged to abide by the Constitution and laws, to respect the rights, freedoms, honor, and dignity of others."

In general, as the basic law of the Republic of Uzbekistan, we can say that our Constitution is the basis of a strong legal and regulatory system of legal socialization of the individual. In particular, its second section, "Fundamental Rights and Duties of Citizens" and the third "Society and the person" section strengthens the legal basis for the legal socialization of the person.

In addition, the adoption of various forms of deviant behavior in our country in recent years, in particular, the anti-corruption law, is important. We believe that the formation of an environment of the uncompromising fight against corruption in the country by both the state and society will increase the effectiveness of the fight against this scourge. Another important aspect of this law is that it has a positive impact not only on the phenomenon of corruption but also on the fight against many deviant behaviors whose origins are related to corruption. We can see that this is specifically stated in Article 5 of the Law on Combating Corruption. This principle is called "The main directions of state policy in the field of combating corruption", which includes: "Raising the legal awareness and legal culture of the population, the formation of an intolerant attitude to corruption in society; - implementation of measures to prevent corruption in all spheres of state and public life; - timely detection of corruption offenses, their cessation, elimination of their consequences, their causes and conditions, ensuring the principle of inevitability of liability for corruption offenses.

The law also stipulates that the prevention and rapid fight against corruption is not only the task of the state, law enforcement agencies, the anti-corruption committee, but also public control, social control, citizens, and citizens' self-government. In this regard, Article 14 of the law states: "The participation of citizens' self-government bodies, non-governmental non-profit organizations, and citizens in the fight against corruption."

"Citizens' self-government bodies, non-governmental non-profit organizations, and citizens can participate in other activities following the law. To implement the measures provided for in this article, non-governmental non-profit organizations shall participate in the activities of interdepartmental commissions and territorial interdepartmental commissions, as well as in the activities of working groups, commissions, and public advisory bodies under state bodies. It should be noted that all these cases have been tested in the world experience and give good results in the practice of countries that have developed effective mechanisms to combat corruption, such as Singapore, Australia, Sweden, Norway, and Denmark. The main emphasis is on inculcating in society the negative perception of corruption, the main problem of the country's development, and the antisocial situation and illegal actions that hinder the effectiveness of the planned reforms. Another article of the law that affects the legal socialization of the individual is Article 16, which emphasizes the issue of legal literacy and the development of a legal culture of the population. Legal consciousness and legal culture, as two important elements of the legal socialization of the individual, give unity to this process.

One of the advantages is that the law, in addition to developing a legal framework for combating corruption, also identifies measures to increase the effectiveness of work in this area. In particular, Article 20 of the law is entitled "Measures to prevent corruption in the field of socio-economic development and entrepreneurship," which sets out the following important tasks. - elimination of administrative and bureaucratic barriers, simplification and efficiency of registration, permitting, and licensing procedures; - creating equal conditions for doing business and preventing unfair competition; - the creation of fair conditions and equal opportunities for the population in the field of education, health, social security, public utilities and other areas of socio-economic development, prevention of corruption offenses; - Introduction of effective mechanisms to combat corruption in non-governmental organizations.

The adoption of the law on combating corruption in our country is of great social, political, legal, and moral significance. This event is one of the most important steps in the development strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan to increase the level of legal socialization of citizens in our society, reduce corruption and related crimes, clean up the moral and legal sphere, increase the effectiveness of reforms, improve living standards, improve the social sphere. plays a crucial role in the implementation of priorities.

Another important legal norm that affects the process of legal socialization of a person and determines its effectiveness is the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Public Oversight". The most important, crucial role in building civil society This law is one of the most important socio-political, legal normative documents adopted in 2018, designed to regulate public control of the social phenomenon and all the processes associated with it...

Article 15 of the law is entitled "Rights and obligations of the subjects of public control", which defines the following:

"Subjects of public control: - Carrying out actions in carrying out public control; - request information from government agencies necessary for public oversight; - to prepare proposals and recommendations based on the results of public control; - to send materials to law enforcement agencies in case of violation of the rights and legitimate interests of citizens, legal entities, the interests of society; "has the right to announce the results of public scrutiny."

This article not only strengthens the position of the individual in society as a subject of socio-political processes but also imposes a strong responsibility on him to exercise control over socio-political processes, has a strong influence on the formation of civic position in people. This article also affects the issue of legitimacy between the state and the citizen, which is one of the important aspects of the legal socialization of the individual. "A lot of legitimacy. "Legitimus" means "lawful,

lawful, lawful." Legitimacy represents trust and agreement between the state and the citizen. The strength of legitimacy between the people and the state is one of the most important deciding factors in the legal socialization of the individual. Because of people's respect and trust in the law, legal norms are formed in many ways based on his trust in the state. Confidence between the subjects of public control plays an extremely important role in increasing the legitimacy between the state and the people. The main condition for the state to strengthen the legal framework of the process of public control, to provide timely and quality solutions to the conclusions and appeals of public control, based on its powers and powers, is to become an effective mechanism. On the other hand, one of the most important factors in the formation of civil society is the active civic position of citizens, public associations, subjects of public control in general, and their active attitude to socio-political processes. Another important article of the Law on Public Oversight, which, in our opinion, has a legal normative basis that enhances the ability to develop and control the legal socialization of the individual, is Article 16. This article of the law is called "Rights and obligations of public authorities in the field of public control." The article states, "Government agencies:

- to receive information from the subjects of public control on the implementation of public control and its results;
- to send to the subjects of public control substantiated objections to the proposals and recommendations contained in the final documents prepared based on the results of public control;
- to post information on issues of public control over its activities on its official websites, as well as in the media. This article defines the rights and obligations of the subjects of public control, the essence of these rights and obligations, how they are reflected in the socio-political life of society, how to properly and effectively organize public control without violating public order. The main criterion is the interests of the state and the people, security, and order.

CONCLUSION

We can think about two important aspects of the process of legal socialization, the social and the legal aspects. In this case, we focused on the role, strength, advantages, and disadvantages of social control, family, community, social environment, mechanisms of self-organization, and self-control in the effective organization of the process of legal socialization, scientific and philosophical analysis of effective mechanisms in this process. On the other hand, we explored the most powerful mechanism of the process of legal socialization, the possibility of organizing, managing, and controlling the process of legal socialization of the legislative, legal regulatory system. In this case, it was possible to compare the two aspects of the object under study, to determine the specificity and advantages through the method of comparison. In conclusion, both social and legal mechanisms are necessary for the organization and control of the process of legal socialization. However, due to the characteristics of our eastern lifestyle and specific social relations, it is possible to effectively use the social mechanisms of the process of legal socialization. After all, in the life of our people from our nationality, there are collectivist traditions that have originated and have been preserved for centuries. They can be used extremely effectively in combating various manifestations of deviant behavior. But at the same time, as in any state governed by the rule of law, in our country the legal normative system remains the strongest and most effective mechanism in the organization and control of various forms of social relations, including the system of legal socialization. Indeed, the legal normative system has two powerful weapons, coercive and punitive, that do not exist in social control. This is the most basic strength of any society.

Bibliography

1. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президенти Шавкат Мирзиёевнинг 2017 йил 19-сентябрь куни Бирлашган Миллатлар Ташкилоти Бош Ассамблеясининг 72-сессиясида нутқи// Халқ сўзи, 2017 йил 20-сентябрь.
2. Бобоев Ҳ.Б, Исломов З.Б. Ҳуқуқ тизими. Ўқув қўлланма. - Т. , 2019.
3. Саидов А.Х. Узбекистан и всеобщая декларация прав человека. -Т.: Адолат, 2018.- Б.146.
4. Ўзбекистон республикаси конституцияси. - Т.: Ўзбекистон, 2018.

5. Махмудова А.Н. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Конституцияси шахс ҳуқуқий ижтимоийлашувининг кучли ҳуқуқий-норматив тизимининг асоси // “Конституция Республикаси Ўзбекистан: Наука, образование и воспитание молодёжи”. Филиал МГУ имени М.В.Ломоносова в городе Ташкенте. Материалы научно-практического семинара. Ташкент, - 2020. - Б.171.
6. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Қонуни. ЎРҚ-419-сон “Коррупцияга қарши кураш тўғрисида” - Т., 2017.3.01.
7. Vafaeva D.B. (Republic of Uzbekistan) The influence of Political consciousness on the formation and development of civil culture . doi: 10.24411/2542-0798-2020-17002 .LXX International correspondence scientific and practical conference «International Scientific Review of the problems and prospects of modern science and education» (Boston. USA. may 20-21, 2020) .с.96-100.doi :10/24411/2542-0798-2020-17002
8. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Қонуни. ЎРҚ-474-сон “Жамоатчилик назорати тўғрисида”- Т., 2018 йил 12-апрель.
9. Барихин А. Большая юридическая энциклопедия. – Москва: Луч, 2009. - С. 352.
10. Махмудова А. Н. и др. Медицина Узбекистана-достижения и перспективы развития сферы //Достижения науки и образования. – 2020. – №. 3 (57).
11. Махмудова А. Н. и др. Роль молодого поколения в формировании современного гражданского общества //Достижения науки и образования. – 2020. – №. 3 (57).
12. Махмудова А. Н. Правовая социализация молодого поколения в правовом государстве //Дистанционные возможности и достижения науки. – 2020. – С. 97.
13. Махмудова А. Н. IX-XII асрларда мовароуннаҳрда илм-фан, маданият ривожлари тарихидан //Yangi O'zbekistonda milliy taraqqiyot va innovasiyalar. – 2022. – С. 272-275.
14. Shokirovna V. S., Nugmanovna M. A. Replacing the works of our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev in the development of Civil Society in our country //Archive of Conferences. – 2021. – Т. 17. – №. 1. – С. 200-203.
15. Махмудова А. Н. Шахс ҳуқуқий ижтимоийлашувидан ижтимоий назорат тушунчаси ва тизими //международный журнал Консенсус. – 2020. – Т. 1. – №. 1.
16. Yevgeniya M., Nugmanovna M. A. Fighting Corruption in the republic of Uzbekistan //Archive of Conferences. – 2021. – Т. 15. – №. 1. – С. 171-173.
17. Nugmanovna M. A. Legal socialization and individual deviant rights: relationships //falsafa va hayot xalqaro jurnal. – С. 49.
18. Nugmanovna M. A., Akbaraliyeva U. G. Family is the basis of society and state //Archive of Conferences. – 2021. – Т. 22. – №. 1. – С. 28-31.
19. Kamariddinova K. A., Nugmanovna M. A. Improving population health the important task of the state //Archive of Conferences. – 2021. – Т. 17. – №. 1. – С. 204-208.
20. Махмудова А. Н., Ахмеджанова Д. М. Вопросы воспитания гармонично развитой молодежи в воззрениях джадидов и современность //Главный редактор. – 2017. – С. 90.
21. Nugmanovna M. A., Kamariddinova K. A. Modern biotechnical problems of medicine and their solutions //Archive of Conferences. – 2021. – Т. 13. – №. 1. – С. 169-173.

FALSAFA VA HAYOT XALQARO JURNAL

1 MAHCYB COH

ФИЛОСОФИЯ И ЖИЗНЬ МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ
СПЕЦИАЛЬНЫЙ НОМЕР 1

PHILOSOPHY AND LIFE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL
SPECIAL ISSUE 1

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Тадқиқот город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000